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SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Plan

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Executive Summary

This document provides a development plan for the tools and data products of the *SP*Ecification, *AN*alysis & *RE*-calibration of *High Energy p*Article Data (**SPEARHEAD**) project. In this plan, it will be laid out which software tools, data products, and catalogues are planned to be developed within the project and provided to the public. Furthermore, this plan will describe the processes, formats, and general procedures that will be adhered throughout the development.

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1 Introduction

The SPEARHEAD project aims to answer three main science questions:

- **SQ1: How are ions and electrons accelerated to the highest energies in solar eruptions, beyond 100 MeV/n and 1 MeV, respectively?**
- **SQ2: What are the processes governing particle release** from acceleration sites in the solar corona?
- **SQ3: What are the key processes of high-energy particle transport** in the interplanetary medium, in the magnetosphere and in the atmosphere?

In order to achieve these goals, three main technical objectives of the project are proposed:

- **TO1: to develop and distribute analysis tools** to extract high-energy particle fluxes from particle detectors designed to operate at lower energies or to yield monitoring data. Response functions of spacecraft instruments will be determined and particle fluxes of the very high energy particles as a function of time and energy will be delivered.
- **TO2: to process and cross-calibrate a large number of data to produce high-energy particle flux datasets and** distribute them to the community.
- **TO3: to validate the data against intermittent direct spectrometer observations.**

This development plan will lay out the technical backgrounds for developing and distributing the tools and data products. Following the technical objectives, there are three different types of technical products this development plan will cover:

- **Analysis tools**, which include on the one hand the necessary software to extract high-energy particle fluxes from particle detectors, for example, Geant4 simulation software. On the other hand belong to this category tools that are more aimed at the general scientific community, and are provided to help access and analyse the new data products and catalogues, for example, Python-based Jupyter Notebooks to (down-) load the new high-energy particle fluxes and do some basic analysis or plotting with them.
- **Data products** derived from the first mention group of software tools. These are intended to be accessed by the general scientific community, and distributed through well-established channels if possible. For example, ASCII or binary CDF files of high-energy particle fluxes.
- **Catalogues** utilizing the newly derived data products in conjunction with existing observations will also be gathered and provided through the project.

2 Development practices

In this chapter, general practices which will be adhered to during the development of the analysis tools, data products, and catalogues will be laid out. The purpose of this is to ensure that all technical products released through the project follow a common, open standard and comply to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable) principles.

2.1 Software development

The analysis software released through the project mainly aims at two different purposes: reproducibility and further scientific analysis. Part of the first purpose is that although all new data products derived during the project will be released following community-standards, the software to obtain them will also be publicly released, allowing to reproduce the results, but also to exploit them, for example, to derive future data products from other observers not undertaken in SPEARHEAD. For this, as well as for further scientific analysis, it is important that already during development adherence to given standards is ensued.

2.1.1 General principles

After an initial internal phase at work-package level, the development will take place in a community-driven open-source manner, using software repositories in a publicly accessible distributed version control system like GitHub or GitLab. For this purpose, an appropriate code of conduct (CoC) will be selected, for example, SunPy's CoC¹ or Astropy's CoC².

Each project partner will designate software maintainers who are responsible for the adherence to the principles described here and to maintain the corresponding software repositories (e.g., monitoring community feedback through issues or reviewing code contributions).

All software developed within the project will be issued a permissive open-source license. To have the same license for all software products is aimed for, but special circumstances might be present that require exceptions.

2.1.2 Languages and platforms

The software will be predominantly relying on the Python programming language. All Python software will be supporting at least Python versions 3.9 to 3.12, which are the maintained versions as of start of the project. All Python tools will support the recent releases of major operating systems (Linux, MacOS, Windows). To assure a unified coding style, automatic code linting following community standards like *PEP8 - Style Guide for Python Code*³ will be applied.

Especially for tools that are aimed at the broader scientific community, Python-based Jupyter Notebooks will be utilized. This document-style coding environment allows to include extensive documentation next to the actual code as well as some graphical user interface (GUI) elements (see Figure 2-1 for an example). Jupyter Notebooks can be either executed locally at the user's computer or in cloud environments. SPEARHEAD will provide with deliverable D6.4 a JupyterHub cloud server specifically for the tools released within the project, which will allow to exploit the tools without local installations.

Monte-Carlo simulations of different instrumentations to derive corresponding response functions for the new data products will be carried out using the well-established, C++ based Geant4⁴ platform. In order to allow the end user to better understand the setup of the simulations and how the response

¹ <https://sunpy.org/coc/>

² https://www.astropy.org/code_of_conduct.html

³ <https://peps.python.org/pep-0008/>

⁴ <https://geant4.org>

functions have been derived, a Geant4 Virtual Machine (G4VM)⁵ system will be provided together with Geometry Description Markup Language (GDML)⁶ files, allowing for example to visualize the used instrument model. The G4VM system provides a well-defined operational environment for executing and analysing the simulations.

Figure 2-1 - Example of a Jupyter Notebook tool that combines Python code, annotations, GUI elements, and output figures

⁵ <https://geant4.lip2ib.in2p3.fr>

⁶ <https://gdml.web.cern.ch/GDML/>

2.1.3 Version control

The main development of the software tools will use git a distributed version control system within openly accessible repositories on GitHub, where the community is invited to actively participate. WP's maintaining repositories are responsible for assigning maintainers of those repositories, who review code submissions and take care of bug reports and other user feedback provided as issues. After significant milestones are achieved, release version (following semantic versioning⁷) will be published. These will be connected to Zenodo⁸. This service, maintained by the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), provides storage and persisting Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for each released software version.

2.1.4 Documentation

Documentation of the software will take place on multiple levels, starting from Python Docstrings⁹ and comments in the actual code. Where appropriate, these will be converted into website-based documentations like Read the Docs¹⁰. Tools provided as Jupyter Notebooks will have the documentation included within the Notebook files itself. The code repositories will provide at least basic instructions on the requirements, installation, and usage of the provided tools, as well as how to contribute to them.

2.1.5 Testing and verification

We aim at having unit tests of individual components (like functions and classes) as well as integration testing for verifying the interaction between different components for all software released through the project. These tests should cover as much of the code base as possible. The testing will be performed, for example, using GitHub Actions when submitting new code. Validation of the software functionality will be continuously throughout the timespan of the project, within the responsible WP's and the whole project. In addition, external members of the scientific community like the advisory board members will be regularly invited to test the software, especially its usability.

2.1.6 Distribution

Next to providing the source code of the tools through openly accessible repositories and per-release Zenodo entries, selected tools may be released as installable Python packages available through the Python Package Index (PyPI)¹¹ and Conda¹². Tools released in the form of Jupyter Notebooks will also be made available through the JupyterHub server provided by the SPEARHEAD project in D6.3. This freely-available server will automatically obtain the necessary files and packages, and allows the community to access the tools directly in a web-browser without the need of any local installations. In the following, integrations of the SPEARHEAD tools into existing or upcoming infrastructures like the large-scale open access infrastructure ESA Datalabs¹³ will be investigated.

2.1.7 User feedback

Obtaining feedback on the development of the tools will be an ongoing process within the project and selected external co-workers, as well as open to the community via GitHub issues or private feedback (e.g., by email). In addition, during the planned workshops special emphasis will be put to obtain feedback on the already available tools from a variety of users.

⁷ <https://semver.org>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org>

⁹ <https://peps.python.org/pep-0257/>

¹⁰ <https://readthedocs.io>

¹¹ <https://pypi.org>

¹² <https://docs.conda.io/projects/conda/en/stable/>

¹³ <https://datalabs.esa.int>

2.1.8 Adapting existing software

The guidelines presented here for software development are aimed at products newly developed within the SPEARHEAD project. In some cases, pre-existing software might be used “as is” or in a modified version, for example, to derive some of the new datasets. For these, adherence to the guidelines is not mandatory, but encouraged.

2.2 Data development, including catalogues

One of the main outputs of the SPEARHEAD project will be novel high-level datasets of high-energy particle observations by various spacecraft within the heliosphere and instruments on Earth. These datasets will allow the scientific community to access energy ranges that have previously scarcely covered. Table 2-1 gives an overview of the datasets planned to be created throughout the project. In addition, the project will compile comprehensive catalogues of near-relativistic ions and relativistic electrons in strong SEP/GLE events as well as FD events from a fleet of different instruments onboard spacecraft, at radial distances from 0.04 to 5 AU. Details on the different datasets and catalogues are described in detail in the Data Management Plan (DMP, D1.2). In this report, only general data development guidelines will be laid out.

Table 2-1: Characteristics of instruments providing the particle flux data to be exploited in SPEARHEAD. The last column gives the status of instrument modelling (“G4” indicates that a Geant4 model is ready for use; “G4a” indicates that an existing Geant4 model needs to be adapted; and “G4i” indicates that the model needs to be implemented).

Target group					
SOHO / ERNE / HED	UTU	H/He: ~13–130 MeV/n O: ~25–200 MeV/n Fe: ~45–200 MeV/n	S: by dE/dx – E E: Total energy measured	1 + 10 × 24 = 241 bins inside a ~120° view cone for H and He.	G4i
SOHO & Chandra/ EPHIN	CAU	H/He: ~4–50 MeV/n, PHA data up to 1 GeV/n electrons: 0.25–10.4 MeV	S: dE/dx – E, dE/dx E: Total energy deposited and dE/dx–dE/dx	36 sectors inside a 83° view cone	SOHO: G4 Chandra: G4a
Ulysses/ KET	CAU	H/He: 2.7– >2000 MeV/n Electrons: 2.5– >300 MeV	S: dE/dx – E, P: dE/dx – C E: Total energy deposited and dE/dx – C method	8 sectors on spinning S/C for two energy channels	G4i
GOES/ HEPAD		H: 330–700, >700 MeV He: 640–850, >850 MeV/n	S: dE/dx – C, dE/dx E: dE/dx – C	N/A	G4
SREM aboard ESA missions		H: >11 MeV Electrons: >0.7 MeV	S, E: dE/dx – dE/dx 15 channels with broad-band response	N/A	G4

<i>Solar Orbiter/ HET</i>	CAU	H and He: 8–200 MeV/n Z > 2: 7–105 MeV/n Electrons: 0.3–15 MeV	S: dE/dx – E E: Total energy deposited	4 view directions on a 3-axis stabilized S/C	G4a
<i>MSL / RAD</i>	CAU	H/He: 6-95 MeV/n O: 10-220 MeV/n Fe: 25-500 MeV	S: dE/dx – E	Mounted on a rover within the Martian atmosphere	G4a
<i>BepiColombo/ SIXS</i>	UTU	H: ~1–30, >30 MeV Electrons: ~60–3000 keV	S: Foil – E; dE/dx – E E: Total energy deposited	5 view directions on a 3-axis stabilized S/C	G4

2.2.1 Formats

All datasets provided through the project will be made available in data formats following suggestions defined by the International Heliophysics Data Environment Alliance¹⁴ (IHDEA). For most datasets, this means releasing them in well-established versatile binary formats like FITS¹⁵, CDF¹⁶, or NetCDF¹⁷, which are already used for many other datasets obtained by the same instruments. In addition, a release in an easily accessible ASCII file format like CSV will be aimed for whenever possible (but might be unreasonable due to file size in some cases). For catalogues, ASCII formats like CSV will be the default file type. Data provided in the binary formats mentioned above will include metadata adhering to standards like the International Solar-Terrestrial Physics (ISTP) guidelines¹⁸ and defined in the DMP (D1.2). When the data is provided in ASCII format, the corresponding metadata will be provided in the header of the file or externally.

2.2.2 Licenses

All datasets and catalogues will be released under a permissive open-source license. To have the same license for all products is aimed for, but special circumstances might be present that require exceptions.

2.2.3 Validation / Feedback

Validation of the datasets and catalogues will be an ongoing process within the project and selected external co-workers. In addition, during the planned workshops special emphasis will be put to obtain feedback on the already available datasets and catalogues from a variety of users.

2.2.4 Distribution

All data products produced by the project will be distributed via data servers hosted at the partner institutes and/or centralized at SPEARHEAD's own virtual server. NOA will establish this server, hosted within the National Data Center (NDC) service in order to meet the needs of the project. The server will collect all products of the project and will be maintained thereafter by NDC. The option to provide here a more sophisticated web-interface to the different SPEARHEAD catalogues will be investigated. Additionally, the aim is to integrate the datasets into the ESA archives. For archival of datasets, the

¹⁴ <https://ihdea.net>

¹⁵ https://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/heasarc/fits_overview.html

¹⁶ <https://cdf.gsfc.nasa.gov>

¹⁷ <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/esdis/esco/standards-and-references/netcdf-classic>

¹⁸ https://spdf.gsfc.nasa.gov/sp_use_of_cdf.html

Zenodo service maintained by CERN will be used, which also provides per-version DOI's, if not already assigned through ESA archives. It's planned to integrate SPEARHEAD high energy particle data and catalogues to other services such as AMDA¹⁹, Propagation tool²⁰, 3Dview²¹, SEPServer²², NMDB²³, International GLE database²⁴, French National Data Center (CDPP)²⁵, and the large-scale open access infrastructure ESA Datalabs²⁶, to the benefit of the large user communities of these services.

2.2.5 Versioning

All datasets and catalogues will be released using a version number. In case changes are made to them (e.g., due to bugfixes or extension to new measurements), this will be reflected by an updated version number. A common way to define the version number is by adding a “_Vxx” suffix to the corresponding filename. In addition, all datasets and catalogues archived at Zenodo automatically get a version number.

¹⁹ <https://amda.irap.omp.eu>

²⁰ <http://propagationtool.cdpp.eu>

²¹ <http://3dview.cdpp.eu>

²² <https://utu.sepserver.eu>

²³ <https://www.nmdb.eu>

²⁴ <https://gle oulu.fi>

²⁵ <https://cdpp-archive.cnes.fr>

²⁶ <https://datalabs.esa.int>

3 Tools to be produced

The products provided through SPEARHEAD with the widest outreach probably will be the new datasets and catalogues that are described in detail in the Data Management Plan (D1.2). Besides them, software products will be provided on the one hand to enable reproducibility, for example, to follow up (or modify) the derivation of one of the new datasets. These tools will be provided following the present guidelines in this document, for example, in public repositories. Furthermore, to increase the understanding of the instrument's response simulations, one of the made available tools will be a Geant4 Virtual Machine (G4VM), providing a well-defined operational environment with the option to visualize the used instrument geometry.

On the other hand, SPEARHEAD will provide additional tools to exploit the new datasets, such as Python software to obtain their data files, load the data into Python structures, and do some basic analysis or visualization, like creating spectra with respect to rigidity or performing velocity dispersion analyses (VDA). For the latter, it is envisioned that a Jupyter Notebook allowing data manipulation such as creating omnidirectional fluxes and combination of data channels will be made available. Once the channels are selected, an onset determination method will be utilized and a linear dependence of the obtained onset times versus the inverse velocity of the particles will be delivered. Furthermore, SPEARHEAD will provide generalized versions of selected methods used in generating the new data products. One example will be a Jupyter Notebook employing a so-called bow-tie method for computing the best estimate of the geometric factors and effective energies of high-energy particle channels. This tool will demonstrate how to apply this method also to datasets not present in this project. Also planned is a tool for the cross-calibration of two datasets resulting in scaling factors

4 Conclusions

In this document, a plan for the development and distribution of datasets, catalogues, and software tools provided by the **SPEARHEAD** project has been presented. Following these guidelines throughout the different WP's will ensure the adherence of **FAIR principles** and **maximise the impact of the project**.

References

D1.2 Data Management Plan, 30-06-2024, SPEARHEAD Deliverable

List of Acronyms/Abbreviations

Acronym/ Abbreviation	Description
AMDA	Automated Multi-Dataset Analysis
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
CDF	Common Data Format
CDPP	French National Data Center
CERN	European ORganization for Nuclear Research
CoC	Code of Conduct
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron
ESA	European Space Agency
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
FD	Forbush Decrease
FITS	Flexible Image Transport System
G4VM	Geant4 Virtual Machine
Geant4	GEometry ANd Tracking
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
GOES	Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HEPAD	High Energy Proton and Alpha Detector
HET	High Energy Telescope
IHDEA	International Heliophysics Data Environment Alliance
ISTP	International Solar-Terrestrial Physics
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
MeV	Megaelectronvolt
MSL	Mars Science Laboratory
NDC	National Data Center
NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
NMDB	Neutron Monitor DataBase

NOA	National Observatory of Athens
OS	Operating System
PyPI	Python Package Index
RAD	Radiation Assessment Detector
SC	Spacecraft
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SQ	Science Question
SREM	Standard Radiation Environment Monitor
TO	Technical Objective
VDA	Velocity Dispersion Analysis
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package